

CoARA

Coalition for Advancing
Research Assessment

CoARA Working Group Webinar *on*

Language-Aware Assessments

21 October 2025

15:30–16:30 CET

PROGRAMME

- 1. CoARA Working Group**
Martine Garnier-Rizet
- 2. Landscape Report**
Gian Maria Greco
- 3. Implementation proposal**
Janne Pölönen
- 4. Questions & Answers**

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WG on multilingualism and language biases in research assessment

Martine Garnier-Rizet

French National Research Agency (ANR)

REFORM OF RESEARCH ASSESSMENT

- [The Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment \(ARRA\) published in 2022](#) has been signed by over 800 organisations from over 50 countries (Europe and beyond)
- The Agreement represents a **public commitment** to the principles, commitments and 5-year timeframe for reforms with action plan
- The agreement establishes a **common direction** for research assessment reform, while respecting organisations' autonomy
- **CoARA (Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment)** offers a space for signatories to learn from others' experiences, to advance the process of research assessment reform in Europe and beyond

MULTILINGUALISM IN ARRA

- **1st core commitment (scope):** “Recognize valuable contributions that researchers make to science and for the benefit of society, including diverse outputs beyond journal publications and **irrespective of the language in which they are communicated**”.
- **3rd core commitment (scope):** inappropriate uses include assessing outputs based on metrics relating to publication venue, format or **language**.
- **6.2 commitment (scope):** “Criteria, tools and processes... should enable recognition of... diverse outputs **in different languages**”
- **Annex 4 – Toolbox:** Value diverse outputs (FAIR data sets, replication studies, registered reports, pre-prints) in different languages **in accordance with the Helsinki initiative**

3. Promote language diversity in research assessment, evaluation, and funding systems.

Make sure that in the process of **expert-based evaluation**, high quality research is valued regardless of the publishing language or publication channel

Make sure that when **metrics-based systems** are utilized, journal and book publications in all languages are adequately taken into account

WG MULTILINGUALISM PARTNERS

- **21 Universities:** Coimbra group, AMU, Hanken, Sorbonne, TAU, TOUR4EU, UMI, UHR, UAntwerp, LEI, UNIMIB, UTU, Nanterre, SU, JYU, Lusófona, UAB, Stockholm, Montréal, Lleida, Warwick
- **5 Research centres and infrastructures:** OPERAS, CNR, CSIC, CNRS, NIFU
- **7 Academies, societies and association of researchers:** TSV, MCAA, ECSPM, Eurodoc, EuroScience, ENRESSH, GYA
- **4 Public or private research funding organisations:** ANR, cOAlition S, FWO, RCF
- **1 Evaluation authorities/agencies:** ANVUR
- **2 Not-for-profit organisations:** EASSH, ISE
- **4 Organisations outside Europe:** CLACSO-FOLEC (Argentina), transl4E (Australia), UNESCO Chair on Open Science (Canada), Fonds de recherche du Québec (Canada, observer)

**44 organisations /
81 experts**
as of June 2025

Co-chairs

- Emanuel Kulczycki (AMU)
- Martine Garnier-Rizet (ANR)
- Gian Maria Greco (MCAA)

Coordination

- Janne Pölönen (TSV)

WG MISSION

- By addressing language diversity and biases in assessment, WG supports the EU (and other) institutions in fulfilling their duty to enhance, promote and **uphold linguistic equity, diversity and non-discrimination** in Europe and globally.
- This requires fostering an academic **culture that values diverse competencies, interactions and communications in all languages** without exclusions or priorities.

The United Nations' Universal Declaration of Human Rights article 27 states that “**everyone has the right freely to participate in the cultural life of the community, to enjoy the arts and to share in scientific advancement and its benefits**”, and this according to Article 2 “**without distinction of any kind, such as... language**”.

The Charter of Fundamental Rights of the EU also places an obligation on the Union to **respect linguistic diversity** (Article 22) **and prohibits discrimination on grounds of language** (Article 21).

European charter for researchers: “Employers and funders of researchers should not discriminate against researchers in any way based on gender, age, ethnic, national or social origin, religion or belief, sexual orientation, **language**, disability, political opinion, social or economic condition”.

WG MAIN OBJECTIVES

1. to **raise awareness** across all fields about the importance of “multilingualism in practice of science, in scientific publications and in academic communications” (UNESCO)
2. to **provide institutions with guidelines, toolbox and implementation proposal** for recognizing, rewarding and incentivizing research carried out and communicated in all languages, and for addressing language biases in metrics, expert-assessment and rankings

Task Forces (TF)

1. TF1: Coordination
2. TF2: Landscape analysis
3. TF3: Policy advice and implementation
4. TF4: Communication

Outputs to expect

- Landscape report
- Implementation proposal
- White paper
- Position paper
- Translations

UNESCO RECOMMENDATION ON OPEN SCIENCE

- **Definition:** Open science is defined as an inclusive construct that combines various movements and practices aiming to **make multilingual scientific knowledge openly available, accessible and reusable for everyone...**
- **Member-state actions:** (l) Promoting a common understanding of open science, associated benefits and challenges, as well as diverse paths to open science. (d) **Encouraging multilingualism in the practice of science, in scientific publications and in academic communications.**

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Landscape Report: Multilingualism and language biases in research assessment

Gian Maria Greco

Marie Curie Alumni Association (MCAA)

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Landscape Report

WG report synthesizes evidence from recent surveys, literature review, and terminology work to examine **how linguistic diversity is practiced and supported across European research systems.**

Six chapters + bibliometric analysis

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Glossary

Outline of a common terminological framework critical to addressing multilingualism effectively within research assessment contexts.

Comprehensive Literature Review

Contextualization of the findings within broader scholarly literature on multilingualism, language biases, and policy implications

Survey of Marie Curie Alumni Association members

Insights into multilingual experiences and practices among early-career and internationally mobile researchers

Italian National Research Council (CNR) Survey

Exploration of
multilingual dynamics
across diverse
scientific fields within
Italy's largest public
research institution

Hungarian Research Network (HUN-REN) Survey

Comparative data and
insights into language
practices and attitudes
within the Hungarian
national research
landscape

Survey of CoARA signatory organizations

Insights into
institutional attitudes
and practices
regarding
multilingualism and
language bias

Key findings

- **English dominance persists.** However researchers routinely operate in multiple languages across teaching, outreach, and local engagement.
- **Multilingual practices remain undervalued** in research assessment, disadvantaging non-native English speakers and locally oriented research.
- Survey evidence (MSCA, CNR, HUN-REN) shows that **English is used for publishing and grants**, while **national languages are crucial for societal impact and education**.

Key findings

- Researchers report language barriers affecting productivity and well-being, with **minimal institutional support for translation or multilingual dissemination**.
- **Institutions acknowledge the problem**, but few have integrated multilingualism into evaluation, peer review, or funding policies.
- Literature warns of “epistemic monoculture” and calls for **balanced multilingualism**, a principle articulated in the WG’s shared glossary.

Glossary

A living glossary of 52 terms with clear definitions relevant to research evaluation.

Key term: Balanced multilingualism

“considering all the communication purposes in all different areas of research, and all the languages needed to fulfill these purposes, in a holistic manner without exclusions or priorities”

A wide literature review
on multilingualism in
research assessment.

Five main areas in the literature

- **Benefits of multilingualism:** Inclusivity, bibliodiversity, societal impact.
- **English dominance and biases:** Inequalities, epistemic monoculture, invisibility.
- **Regional and disciplinary differences:** Varied practices across fields and regions.
- **Policy recommendations:** Reward non-English outputs, adapt metrics, narrative CVs.
- **Technology and AI:** Machine translation, inclusion, complement to policy.

Survey of Marie Curie Alumni Association members

- ~**27%** of the Marie Curie Alumni Association (MCAA) surveyed members agreed that **language barriers “disrupted their workflow,”** and roughly **33% felt a negative impact on their well-being.**
- ~**95% of respondents use English** for peer-reviewed publications, and **94%** for scholarly presentations
- ~**49%** of respondents **relied on professional translation services, or automated tools or help from colleagues** in publishing or communicating in English for a scholarly audience

**Consiglio Nazionale
delle Ricerche**

- 910 respondents (13% response rate).
- CNR scientists almost all work in multilingual settings. In Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH), most researchers balance Italian with other languages, reflecting local cultural engagement and global dialogue. In STEM and life sciences, English is overwhelmingly dominant for publishing and collaborations.
- Translation is common in SSH: **36% of SSH respondents had their work translated.**

Hungarian Research Network (HUN-REN) Survey

- 211 responses (6% of ~3,500 researchers).
- Nearly all HUN-REN researchers (95.8%) use Hungarian and other languages in their work.
- **English overwhelmingly dominates in publications:** 40% of respondents publish entirely in English, and another 29.7% publish 90% in English.

Survey of CoARA signatory organizations

- 81 CoARA members from 30 countries replied (14.3% of those invited).
- Nearly 60% said their institution considers multilingualism “to some extent” in current assessment policies , only 8 said “to a large extent,” and about 13 said “not so much.”
- 61 institutions answered “No” to favoring certain languages in evaluation (i.e. they profess not to limit outputs by language).

+Bibliometric analysis of global research output

- **WEB OF SCIENCE**

- English: 93 %
- Other: 7 %

- **SCOPUS**

- English: 88 %
- Other: 12 %

- **OPENALEX**

- English: 75 % - 67 %*
- Other: 25 % - 33 %*

Brasil, A. (2024). [Exploring the landscape of multilingualism through bibliometrics](#), CoARA WG Webinar 26 Sep 2024

*Céspedes, L. et al. (2025). [Evaluating the Linguistic Coverage of OpenAlex](#), JASIST

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Implementation Proposal for Language-aware Assessments

Janne Pölönen

Federation of Finnish Learned Societies (TSV)

INTRODUCTION

- **Implementation proposal is aimed at leadership and management** of higher education institutions, research and funding organisations to facilitate implementation of CoARA commitments.
- The document presents **four proposals for the possible implementation** of language-aware assessments, including **concrete actions and steps** to guide the implementation

Five annexes to support the implementation proposal

- **I Glossary** of multilingualism for research assessment
- **II Checklist** of multilingualism policies and initiatives
- **III Toolbox** on language-aware assessments
- **IV Landscape report** on Multilingualism and Language Biases in Research Assessment
- **V Exploring** Multilingualism in Research: A **Survey** to researchers at the National Research Council of Italy

1: MAKE MULTILINGUALISM A VALUE IN RESEARCH ASSESSMENT

- **Action 1:** set up a committee, or assign the task to an existing body, for promoting language awareness, multilingualism and addressing language bias in research assessment as outlined in this implementation proposal in your organisation (see Annex II and IV)
- **Action 2:** incorporate multilingualism into your organisation's CoARA Action plan
- **Action 3:** create or update relevant strategies and policies of your organisation

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- **Step A:** review international and national policies and initiatives your organisation has signed or adhered to (see see Annex II)
 - **Step B:** consult international and national expert bodies, committees or societies on language and multilingualism policies and practices
 - **Step C:** review and update (if needed), strategies and policies of your organisation in light of the international and national policies

2: ASSESS AND IMPROVE LANGUAGE DIVERSITY, COMPETENCES AND PRACTICES

- **Action 1:** create an overview of active and passive language skills, practices and needs in your organisation
- **Action 2:** identify gaps and priorities for improvement
- **Action 3:** develop capacity, services and infrastructure to support language skills and multilingualism

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- **Step A:** identify strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats in the language skills and competences, languages used and needed in your organisation
 - **Step B:** identify and prioritise areas of improvement and create a roadmap for better supporting the language skills and competences, improving language practices and meeting the language needs of target audiences

3: CREATE EXPECTATIONS AND CRITERIA FOR MULTILINGUALISM

- **Action 1:** implement criteria that recognise and reward contributions in any language as well as in many languages (e.g. through translations or adaptations)
- **Action 2:** positively value contributions to development of scientific terminology regardless of language
- **Action 3:** recognise as merit or establish awards for promoting multilingualism in research process, outputs (e.g. data, publications), teams and collaboration, conferences and events, teaching and education, community engagement, publication channels (e.g. journals, books), and assessments

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- **Step A:** explicitly state that research contributions are recognised irrespective of language and that multilingual communication strategies and translanguaging practices are positively valued
 - **Step B:** avoid criteria and indicators that explicitly use or implicate communication language as a proxy of quality, impact or internationality of contributions
 - **Step C:** recognise and reward citizen and community engagement, outreach activities and collaboration, public science communication, and media presence in the language(s) of the local/regional/national communities

4: INTEGRATE MULTILINGUALISM INTO ASSESSMENT PROCESSES

- **Action 1:** support multilingual communication throughout assessment process
- **Action 2:** consider language diversity and competences relevant to assessment context when selecting and instructing evaluators
- **Action 3:** make multilingualism integral part of quantitative and qualitative information supporting assessment

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- **Step A:** recruit diverse pools of evaluators who are attentive of language diversity and challenges and are capable of assessing contributions in the relevant languages
 - **Step B:** make evaluators aware of language biases and disadvantages for second language users, and explicitly instruct evaluators to focus on the scientific quality rather than the language of communication

ANNEX I: GLOSSARY OF MULTILINGUALISM FOR RESEARCH ASSESSMENT

- Academic freedom
- Balanced multilingualism
- Bias
- Bibliodiversity
- Covert linguistic racism
- Diglossia
- Disparity
- Diversity
- Epistemic diversity
- Epistemic domination
- Epistemic oppression
- Epistemic violence
- Epistemicide
- Epistemological monoculture
- Epistemological plurality
- Ethnic accent bullying
- Impact
- Interdisciplinarity
- Intersectionality
- Language bias
- Linguicide
- Linguicism
- Linguistic disadvantage
- Linguistic diversity
- Linguistic hegemony
- Linguistic imperialism

- Linguistic injustice
- Linguistic prejudice
- Linguistic privilege
- Linguistic repertoire
- Linguistic stereotyping
- Monolingualism
- Multidisciplinarity
- Multilingual publishing
- Multilingualism
- Pluriknowledging
- Plurilinguaging
- Plurilinguism
- Publication bias
- Quality
- Research assessment
- Research culture
- Research ethics
- Research integrity
- Research on research
- Researcher
- Reviewer bias
- Scientific diglossia
- Transdisciplinarity
- Transknowledging
- Translanguaging
- Undercoverage bias

Linguistic injustice	A situation that arises when speakers of some languages are disadvantaged relative to others (e.g. when English is used for scholarly communication, non-Anglophones face more hurdles than native English speakers)	(Hyland, 2016; Politzer-Ahles et al., 2016)
Linguistic prejudice	A bias against groups based on their language or linguistic background (e.g. against non-Anglophones in peer review or scholarly publishing)	(Poltzer-Ahles et al., 2020)
Linguistic privilege	An advantage afforded to speakers of one language (e.g. English) in a certain setting or for a certain purpose (e.g. scholarly publishing)	(Soler, 2019)

ANNEX II: CHECKLIST OF MULTILINGUALISM POLICIES & INITIATIVES

- [Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment](#)
- [Universal Declaration of Human Rights](#)
- [Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union](#)
- [UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science](#)
- [G20 Recommendations on inclusion, diversity and combating inequalities in science, technology and innovation](#)
- [European Charter for Researchers](#)
- [Council conclusions on research assessment and implementation of open science](#)
- [CLACSO–FOLEC Declaration of Principles](#)
- [Helsinki Initiative on Multilingualism in Scholarly Communication](#)
- [Leiden Manifesto for Research Metrics](#)
- [Barcelona Declaration on Open Research Information](#)
- [ECSPM Declaration for Multilingualism in Higher Education](#)

ANNEX II: EUROPEAN CHARTER FOR RESEARCHERS

The [European Charter for Researchers](#), established in 2025 and updated in the Council Recommendation of 18 December 2023, outlines principles for attractive and sustainable research careers within the European Research Area (ERA). While the Recommendation

- **2005 General principles and requirements applicable to employers and funders, Non-discrimination:** “Employers and/or funders of researchers will not discriminate against researchers in any way on the basis of gender, age, ethnic, national or social origin, religion or belief, sexual orientation, language, disability, political opinion, social or economic condition.”
- **2023 Pillar 2 – researchers assessment, recruitment and progression, 3 Selection, Non-discrimination:** “Employers and funders of researchers should not discriminate against researchers in any way based on gender, age, ethnic, national or social origin, religion or belief, sexual orientation, language, disability, political opinion, social or economic condition.”

ANNEX V: EXPLORING MULTILINGUALISM IN RESEARCH

- A Survey to researchers at the National Research Council of Italy
- Full questionnaire for conducting an institutional survey on language skills,, practices and attitudes towards multilingualism
- The survey has been conducted in Hungarian by HUN-REN

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Questions & Answers

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Working Group on Multilingualism and Language Biases in Research Assessments

**OPEN CONSULTATION ON THE
IMPLEMENTATION PROPOSAL FOR
LANGUAGE-AWARE ASSESSMENTS**

PROVIDE FEEDBACK UNTIL 6 NOVEMBER 2025

